

Managerial Effectiveness: Content, Evaluation and Recommendations

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ABSTRACT: In a market economy, a manager is primarily a person with a certain level of qualification, authority and responsibility to implement a company's development strategy, such as production volume, profit, profitability, labor productivity. The article describes the role of management in the effective operation of enterprises, the scientific approaches of scientists in this area, evaluation indicators. Also, the indicators of the enterprise as an object of specific research were analyzed and problems in the work of the manager were indicated. Recommendations are given to overcome the existing problems in management activities.

KEYWORDS: Human Factor, Managerial Labor, Indicators of Evaluation of Leadership Results, Social Efficiency, Economic Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Thanks to the ongoing reforms for sustainable and efficient development of the economy, in a short period of time to carry out profound structural changes in the economy, development of production and services, income growth, sustainable development of small business and private entrepreneurship, strengthening the banking and financial system. Significant progress has been made in the development of scientific projects.

In achieving these successes, the role of existing businesses plays an important role. At present, there are 475197 enterprises and organizations in the country by type of economic activity, in which 13239.6 thousand people work, contributing to the achievement of these achievements.

Therefore, one of the key factors in the development of the economy of enterprises is the human factor. Today, the management of labor potential in enterprises, their effective use requires modern management. The number, potential, formation, development and composition of employees play an important role in the management of the enterprise. In particular, the effectiveness of human resources has a direct impact on the results of the enterprise.

Assessing the effectiveness of managerial work is one of the most pressing issues today. An effective manager should pay equal attention to two areas of his activity: interaction with the external environment and improving the internal environment of the organization. In this sense, evaluating employee performance helps to develop

relationships within the company. It is therefore no coincidence that the increasing focus on personnel evaluation and certification is currently on the rise. Managers thus seek to strengthen internal ranks and increase organizational resilience in adverse economic conditions.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that "... business entities and new jobs created in each sector, sector, region and district will be the main criterion in assessing the activities of the heads of these structures ...".¹

Reforming the management system in the sectors of the economy in our country requires radically new qualities, first of all, new knowledge, skills and abilities of management staff. The special role and importance of the manager depends on the competition between producers of goods and services.

In the context of the transition of our economy to market relations, there are problems with its reform. In particular, the existing problems in enterprises and firms, including low competitiveness of products, significant inefficiency of business organization, all its manifestations lag behind developed countries in the field of management. Management methods in enterprises and organizations in our country are often outdated. There is a great interest in evaluating the mental work of managers. Also, the role of labor performance evaluation to increase the efficiency of enterprises and organizations is constantly increasing, which can be seen for the following reasons: the difficulty of measuring management activity as a type of intellectual labor

¹Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. "People's Word" January 25, 2020, №19 (7521).

relative to physical labor of workers, operators and other categories of technicians. In this case, there are almost no production standards that are directly related to the manager's managerial work; the relationship between the performance of the individual manager and the overall end result becomes increasingly difficult in the context of an in-depth division of labor. Requires the use of modern methods in the process of evaluating the performance of managers; the increasing complexity and importance of management work due to the multiplicity and diversity of functions, including professional differentiation, implies an increasing role in evaluating the work of all categories of managers. Based on the above, one of the most pressing issues today is the assessment and comprehensive analysis of the performance of management staff.

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

In economic theory, efficiency is most often determined based on the goals set as a function of the results achieved and the resources spent on it.

There is a lot of controversy in the economic literature about the identity of the concepts of "efficiency" and "productivity" of managerial work. Some authors, under the effectiveness of managerial labor, understand its conditional productivity, which is expressed by the ability of labor to perform the corresponding work per unit of time and to ensure efficiency, reliability and optimality of production management.

Other authors note that the efficiency of managerial work, in addition to its productivity, characterizes the quality of work, their complexity and timeliness of execution, also assuming that the efficiency of managerial work is determined by the productivity of the collective of a given enterprise.

Oligin-Nesterov V.I. believes that “the comparison of the costs of social labor in production management to the volume of functions performed characterizes the productivity of managerial labor, and comparison with the quantitative results of production determines the efficiency of management as a whole.”²

L.A. Kostin the category "labor productivity" proposes to refer only to material production. Labor

efficiency is a broader indicator characterized by the ratio of the result (effect) to labor costs in all spheres of its activity.³

The "efficiency" of managerial labor in comparison with its "productivity" is undoubtedly a broader concept. In addition, labor productivity as an indicator is acceptable only for those types of labor, the results of which are quantifiable. However, it is impossible to judge the performance of a manager based on the amount of processed information, the number of issued orders and orders using the performance indicator. Consequently, the productivity of managerial labor is one of the most important, but not the only indicator of its effectiveness.

According to N.I.Churakova, management efficiency is a complex and diverse concept, the meaning of which is that the entire management process, from setting a goal to the end result of an activity, should be carried out with the lowest cost and (or) with the greatest efficiency.⁴

In the dictionary "Management of the Economy" edited by R.A.Belousov, the effectiveness of management activity is defined as "the ratio of its useful result (effect) and the volume of resources used - spent for this resources in a broad sense - labor time (work time and qualifications of managers), materials (raw materials, semi-finished products), energy, financial resources".⁵

The ratio of the elements of efficiency (effect and costs) indicates the following possibilities of its increase: at constant costs and increasing the effect; with constant effect and cost reduction; with a faster increase in the effect compared to the increase in costs.

Management efficiency is a complex category that reflects the relationship and interaction of the results of management activities and the costs incurred in it (use of material, financial, labor and other resources), says one of our economists N.Q.Yuldashev.⁶

The constant control over the activities of his subordinates by the manager has a positive effect. Assessment is a set of several instrumental systems that are strongly linked to the basic functions of object management. Evaluation implies the existence of evaluation criteria and an evaluation scale.

² Oligin-Nesterov V.I. The use of economic laws in production management. - M.: "Thought", 1980. – page 153.

³ L.A. Kostin Improving labor efficiency in the new business environment. - M.: "Thought", 1984. – page 39.

⁴ Churakova N.I., Sinyakova M.G., Lagutina E.E., Slobodchikova PS Social and economic efficiency of

personnel management in an organization: a tutorial. Ekaterinburg, 2013, page 10. (total 153 pages.)

⁵ Economic Management: Dictionary / Ed. R. A. Belousova. [Text] .- M., 1999

⁶ N.Q.Yuldashev, V.I. Nabokov, O.A.Aripov, O.Ahmedov. Management theory. Namangan.: 2016. page 209 (total 436 pages)

Table 1. List of performance indicators of individual position managers and specialists on staff quality and performance⁷

Position	List of performance appraisal indicators	Evaluation of staff quality indicators
The head of the organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - profit - profit growth - production profitability - indicators of capital turnover - market share -competitiveness of products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - professional knowledge and skills - attitude to work - efficiency - striving to improve working methods, the ability to introduce innovations - ability to coordinate and interact
Line managers - heads of production, workshops, foremen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - execution of planned tasks in terms of volume and nomenclature - dynamics of production volume - dynamics of labor productivity - reduced production costs - the number of complaints and their dynamics - indicators of the quality of products - amount and loss from downtime - employee turnover rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - initiative - diligence - sociability -analytic skills - use your time efficiently - objectively evaluates his subordinates - explains goals to subordinates
Human Resources Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - labor productivity and its dynamics - reducing the standard labor intensity of manufactured products - the proportion of technically sound norms - the level of wages per unit of production and its dynamics - employee turnover rate and its dynamics - number of vacancies - the number of applicants for one vacant place - indicators for training and advanced training of personnel - personnel costs in production costs - specific gravity and dynamics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high level of accuracy and precision - a responsibility - initiative - relationships with others - interest in work - professional competence - honesty, decency - creates trust - takes on complex cases - reacts to changes in the career

Modern principles of management have a unique expression and independent nature in the management of employees, work teams, the processes of relations in production.⁸

Management principles provide for a clear regulation of the rights and responsibilities of employees, as well as managers of various links in the management system of the enterprise. The responsibilities of the manager and employees should also be known during the work process. This is important in achieving the goals of the enterprise.⁹

Management performance appraisal is the process of determining the effectiveness of employees' performance in carrying out organizational tasks, which allows them to

obtain information for subsequent management decisions.¹⁰

The effectiveness of managerial work is a social and economic category, since the effect of managerial activity is not limited only to economic results. The social effect is also of great importance. In this regard, two types of managerial labor efficiency are distinguished: economic and social. Their independence is, of course, relative, since they are in close unity and interconnection. In terms of their role in ensuring the effective functioning of the organization, they are not equivalent: social efficiency as generalizing, final, and in this sense the main one; economic - as primary, initial, and in this sense, basic.

⁷ Previous literature. page278

⁸ M.M.Yuldasheva. "Improving personnel management in corporate structures in the context of modernization of the national economy." 08.00.13 - "Management and marketing", i.f.n. academic degree dissertation. TDIU, -T ;, 2010. -page 151.

⁹ P.V. Zabelin and others. "Entrepreneurial management". Educational and practical guide. M.: PRIOR. 1999.

¹⁰ Krikun O. A. Self-management: a tutorial / O. A. Krikun. - Kh.: V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, 2014. -page 276. (total 344 pages.)

Figure 1. Types of labor efficiency of management staff.

To assess the effectiveness of the manager's activities, production and economic indicators are used, which describe criteria such as the quality, volume and timing of production (services provided). The most universal criterion for evaluating the performance of managers is the net profit index. However, it is also necessary to take into account a number of other indicators: the use of fixed and working capital, investment efficiency, staff turnover and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the main factors of the efficiency of enterprises is the efficiency of the management staff. In our research, the analysis of the effectiveness of the work of management staff,

the effectiveness of the work of the manager of the design and research enterprise "Shams". At the same time, indicators and a database of our research work were formed. Based on the collected data, methods such as statistical observation, comparison and logical approach were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We have analyzed several indicators that are taken into account in assessing the effectiveness of the manager's work - profit, profit growth, capital turnover, market share.

In the process of the design and research and production enterprise "Shams" the profit of the enterprise is formed as follows.

Table 2. Analysis of the net profit of the research and production enterprise "Shams" and the factors influencing its change¹¹

№	Indicators	2018 year	2019 year	2020 year	The difference between 2020 and 2018, (+; -)
1	Proceeds from the sale of products (goods, works and services)	703160.5	678924.6	486956	- 216204.5
2	Current expenses	500827	671463	592818.7	91991.7
a)	Administrative expenses	95000	105000	92000	- 3000
б)	Other operating expenses	405827	566463	500818.7	94991.7
3	Profit (loss) from general economic activity	202333.5	17774.9	- 105862,7	- 308196.2
4	Profit tax and other taxes and deductions	24280.02	2132.8	-	24280.02
Net profit for the current year		178053.48	15642.1	- 105862.7	- 283916.18

According to the table, in 2020 the company incurred a loss of 105.86 million soums. One of the main reasons for this is that in the context of the pandemic, the amount of

revenue decreased compared to the previous year as a result of reduced demand for project development in the main activities of the enterprise. Periodic costs have increased

¹¹ Annual report of Shams Research and Production Enterprise. 2018-2020 yy.

compared to the previous year, while other operating costs include health care and additional disbursements up to the amount of actual wages established by law in the event of temporary incapacity for work. This means that the company

incurred a loss of 105.8 million soums in 2020. This means that compared to 2018, the company's profit decreased by 283.9 million soums.

Table 3. Capital turnover of Shams project-research and production enterprise (thousand uzбек soums)

№	Indicators	2018 year	2019 year	2020 year
1	Capital turnover of the enterprise	98285	151761	44872.8
2	An absolute difference from the previous year	84518.2	53476	- 106888.2

According to the table, the capital turnover of the enterprise in 2017 amounted to 13766.8 thousand soums. In 2018, 2019, the capital turnover of the enterprise increased by 84518.2 and 53476 thousand soums, respectively, compared to previous years. The impact of the pandemic in 2020 led to

a decrease in capital turnover and decreased by 106.9 million soums compared to 2019.

There are about 30 project development enterprises in the region. We analyze the market share of the design and research enterprise "Shams" on the basis of the following table.

Table 4. Market share of Shams Research and Production Enterprise

№	Indicators	2018 year	2019 year	2020 year	The difference from 2020 to 2018 (+;-)
1	Revenue from sales of goods (goods, works and services), thousand soums	703160.5	678924.6	486956	- 216204.5
2	Total project development market share, in percentage	3.4	3.0	2.2	- 1.2

According to the table, the market share of the research and production enterprise "Shams" has decreased in recent years. It can be seen that in 2020, the market share of the enterprise decreased by 1.2 percent compared to 2018, or 64.7%. Compared to 2019, it was 0.8 percent lower.

As a result of the above analysis, the efficiency of management work at the Shams research and production enterprise in 2019-2020 decreased compared to the previous year. The pandemic, which took place on a global scale in 2020 and still retains a certain degree of impact, did not bypass the activities of the enterprise. The market share of enterprises developing enterprise projects is also low, which indicates the need to try to increase its market share. This means that the head of the enterprise must take into account the preconceived notions in different situations in order to avoid a decrease in the economic efficiency of management in such situations.

Also, as a result of the general analysis of the results of managerial work, it was found that a number of factors can affect the effectiveness of management: natural-biological, socio-economic, technical and organizational, socio-psychological, market factors.

At the same time, the following qualities of leadership have a negative impact on the effectiveness of the work of a manager: politeness, cultural upbringing and lack of ethics; low culture of communication with people of different positions and status; disrespect, allowing rudeness; inability to clearly formulate the tasks assigned to subordinates; inability to express an independent opinion; inability to apply

knowledge in practice; inability to find ways out of difficult situations; lack of experience in decision making; inability to solve strategic and tactical tasks, inability to formulate future plans, and so on.

It is desirable that these problems be addressed in order to increase the efficiency of managerial labor.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This article explores one of the most pressing issues of modern managers - improving management efficiency. In general, the result of the work of the employee of the management is characterized by the degree to which the goal of management is achieved at the lowest cost. The main purpose of management performance appraisal is to improve the quality of work of employees, a process that is of great importance both for long-term wage setting and for training and development purposes.

We recommend the following recommendations for the data obtained from the study and the results of their analysis. To increase the efficiency of management activities in enterprises:

- scientifically based distribution of labor under the head;
- organization and repair of workplaces, their rational order and coverage of equipment, organization of an effective system of workplace maintenance;
- improving working conditions, ensuring the elimination of harmful production, the rational organization of heavy physical, psychological and emotional, industrial

environment, the formation of a system of occupational safety and health;

- optimal use of working time, optimization of work and rest regimes;

- rationalization of labor processes, introduction of optimal methods of labor, including understanding of labor processes by various methods and techniques, selection of the most effective methods of labor, their improvement and organization of industrial training, training; expansion and updating of scientific and technical information;

- strengthening labor discipline, which provides for the strengthening of production and labor discipline, the formation of a sense of responsibility, the formation of creative initiative and other forms of active participation of employees in the life of enterprises and organizations;

- creation of an effective information system in the internal and external environment of the enterprise, the development of an effective communication system in the enterprise;

- increasing the social efficiency of managerial work; to apply new ways of motivation in practice, to teach team members to work together, to voluntarily fight for the effective result of the enterprise;

- to form the most optimal variant of the enterprise management structure;

- overcoming the psychological barrier between the manager and subordinates;

- we believe that it should create a satisfactory socio-emotional environment in the community, friendly relations and so on.

Hence, effective management affects all aspects of an organization's operations. Therefore, each company should evaluate the effectiveness of management and develop various measures to improve it. This helps to increase the efficiency of the whole enterprise.

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